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OSM Science 2025: Diversifying the Study of OpenStreetMap

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The first Academic Track of State of the Map (SotM) was organized at SotM 2018 in Milan, Italy. Since then, it has been held regularly, continuing even during the Covid-19 pandemic. In 2023, the track was hosted within SotM EU and renamed OSM Science to emphasize its role as the only academic meeting dedicated exclusively to research on and with OpenStreetMap (OSM). From 2018 to 2023, the hosting locations—Milan, Italy; Heidelberg, Germany; Florence, Italy; and Antwerp, Belgium (with Cape Town omitted, as SotM 2020 was moved online due to the pandemic)—all lay within Central Europe. This concentration reflects broader publication patterns, as most OSM-related academic papers are authored by scholars based in Europe [1]. The 2024 and 2025 editions, however, mark a departure from this trend, with OSM Science following SotM to Nairobi, Kenya in 2024 and Manila, the Philippines in 2025. These shifts create a unique opportunity to explore the implications of expanding OSM Science to new regions. They raise important questions about whether holding the meeting outside Europe alters the nature of the event and whether such moves influence representation—shaping who authors contributions, what topics are investigated, and which case study locations are highlighted. This must also take into account the growing role of remote participation, normalized during the Covid-19 years.

Across all editions of the Academic Track/OSM Science [2–6], 96 abstracts have been published (excluding 2018, which released no proceedings, and including the forthcoming 2024 edition). Europe and North America dominate, with individuals affiliated to institutions there authoring between 60% and 94% of abstracts (mean 83%; counts include co-authorship across continents). Asian institutions appear in four of seven editions—peaking at 30% in 2020 and 2025—while African institutions appear in only three: 2020 (30%), 2023 (6%), and 2024 (9%). The unusually high African share in 2020 reflects the

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original plan to host SotM in Cape Town, though the event shifted online. Regional imbalance has in fact deepened: during the Covid and immediate post-Covid years (2020–2023), Europe/North America’s share rose from 60% to 94%, despite remote presentation lowering formal barriers. The 2021 edition, designed from the outset as online, included no Asian or African authors. Only when the conference moved outside Europe did the share of Europe/North America decline—to 91% in 2024 (Kenya) and 80% in 2025 (Philippines). Geography therefore continues to matter: hosting in new regions demonstrably increases the visibility of underrepresented voices.

The question is whether shifts in participation also influence content. One indicator is the geography of case studies. The editions with the highest shares of African or Asian case studies are 2020 (50%) and 2024 (37%)—the two African editions. This aligns with a broader pattern: authors generally study locations close to home [1]. Across all editions (including 2025), only 17% of European or North American authors addressed African or Asian case studies, compared with 60% among African and Asian authors. A second indicator is research focus. We classified abstracts into four categories: (1) basic OSM research—implementation and data quality; (2) OSM-oriented research—studies of contribution patterns, contributors, or tools to guide mapping; (3) social research—analyses of OSM’s societal impact and context; and (4) reviews (one abstract, omitted from analysis). Over time, basic research dominates, OSM-oriented work declines, and social research grows, with little connection to conference location. Differences by author affiliation, however, are more striking. Among European and North American authors, basic (43%) and OSM-oriented (39%) work are balanced. Among African and Asian authors, basic research is far more prevalent (67%) and OSM-oriented much less so (20%). This suggests a structural gap: in the Global North, data quality and implementation are increasingly seen as “solved,” with attention shifting to machine learning and GeoAI; elsewhere, foundational challenges remain pressing. Expanding representation therefore potentially enriches OSM Science by reintroducing perspectives that highlight persistent blind spots in mainstream discourse.

The 2025 abstracts illustrate how origins shape the agenda. Among European and North American contributions, work spans the full range of research. In basic OSM research, Schultz et al. [7] introduce OSMLanduse, the first EU-wide 10 m land-use dataset, harmonizing OSM semantics with Sentinel-2 imagery through deep learning, achieving high accuracy and offering a reproducible framework for continental mapping (classified as European despite Asian co-authors, as the lead and most authors are Europe-based). Williams & Priestnal [8] present PlaceCrafter, which uses OSM POI data to generate platial regions that reflect how people use space, supporting more flexible regional analysis. Zohar et al. [9] develop a geocoding framework integrating OSM and GeoNames to localize wildfire-related tweets during the 2016 Haifa fire, demonstrating OSM’s multilingual, fine-grained features as critical for hyperlocal monitoring. Kašík [10] contributes a city-scale extrinsic quality assessment for Brno, revealing the limits of ISO 19157 for qualitative attributes while offering an alternative pathway for municipal-level OSM quality assessment.

OSM-oriented studies include Štampach et al.’s [11] user testing of the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team’s (HOT) fAIr tool, showing that manual mapping in JOSM was superior overall but also highlighting fAIr’s accessibility for beginners and potential as a complementary tool. Similarly, Herrera-Murillo et al. [12] analyze HOT Tasking Manager projects, identifying uncoordinated individual mapping by beginners as dominant and suggesting design improvements to better support collaboration.

In social research, Mooney et al. [13] examine how major LLMs and chatbots portray OSM, finding generally positive sentiment—emphasizing openness, coverage, and community—while also noting concerns about uneven quality and completeness. Nguyen et al. [14] describe EUthMappers, an ERASMUS+ project embedding OSM-based mapping into STEM education across five European countries, engaging secondary students in humanitarian mapping and demonstrating OSM’s role in education and civic engagement.

By contrast, Asian contributions focus on basic OSM research. Ahmed [15] develops an unsupervised machine learning framework to assess OSM data quality in Dhaka, clustering contributors based on behavioral metadata and showing that activity, thematic focus, and spatial distribution strongly predict reliability. Maliha [16] produces accessibility maps for disaster preparedness in Dhaka, identifying safe open spaces and building a routing model using OSM roads and buildings.

The 2025 edition thus reflects topic-related trends across earlier years. Yet beyond the absence of OSM-oriented and social research in the Asian abstracts, deeper contrasts emerge in motivation and method. For example, Kašík’s [10] quality assessment assumes the availability of authoritative data, while Ahmed [15] addresses contexts where such data are scarce. Similarly, the implementation-oriented study differs both in aims and techniques: Maliha [16] is motivated by urgent local needs, whereas Schultz et al. [7] and Williams & Priestnal [8] develop more generic systems. European and North American authors employ advanced methods such as deep learning [7], fuzzy clustering [8], and NLP [9], while Asian contributions rely on established approaches such as K-Means clustering, Principal Component Analysis [15] and network analysis [16].

Notably, all three Asian abstracts [15,16] were authored by scholars based in Bangladesh. This pattern is not unique: all South American contributions across past editions originated in Brazil, largely from a single research group. While this concentration limits the robustness of comparative analysis, it illustrates how holding OSM Science outside Europe can support nascent research groups by exposing their members to broader trends and facilitating interaction with established teams. To realize this potential, however, gaps in motivation and methods need to be bridged. This remains constrained: only 6 (43%) of the abstracts authored by African and Asian researchers included European or North American co-authors. Another challenge lies in ensuring physical participation: only 30% of the 2025 talks were delivered in person, compared with 60% in 2024 and 71% in 2023. Diversifying conference locations creates opportunities for new voices, but sustained progress requires stronger infrastructures for fostering collaboration and supporting researcher mobility—not only from Europe and North America outward, but also in the reverse direction. Despite technological advances that have reduced barriers to remote interaction, our analysis underscores that structural constraints on mobility and collaboration remain pressing challenges, not only for OSM Science meetings but for the field as a whole.

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OSMLanduse: A Dataset of European Union Land Use at 10 m Resolution Derived from OpenStreetMap and Sentinel-2

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Spatially resolved present-day land use is essential for climate-mitigation tracking, food-system monitoring, and spatial planning. Yet Europe still relies on CORINE Land Cover (CLC), a 100 m inventory updated on a six-year cycle that under-represents urban micro-mosaics [1]. In parallel, new 10 m land-cover products—ESA WorldCover and Google/WRI Dynamic World—excel at spectral separation but provide limited land-use semantics [2,3]. We aim to fuse OSM's human semantics with Sentinel-2's spatial grain to close this gap. The data is available at <https://doi.org/10.11588/data/IUTCDN> and the code here <https://github.com/schultzheidelberg/OpenStreetMap-land-use-for-Europe-2020>.

We present OSMLanduse, to our knowledge the first EU-wide 10 m land-use map that combines OpenStreetMap (OSM) with Sentinel-2 through a fully open workflow. Using the March 2020 OSM planet snapshot, we normalized tags into 13 CLC-compatible classes, directly labeling 61.8% of the EU28 (status as of March 2020). For unlabeled areas, we trained per-country residual convolutional neural networks on cloud-masked, multi-temporal Sentinel-2 medoid composites and mosaicked predictions with original OSM vectors into a seamless raster–vector hybrid. GeoTIFF tiles, training rasters, and the OSM→CLC translation table are openly released alongside code (GPL-3.0), trained weights, and a web viewer.

Map accuracy was assessed with 4,616 stratified reference points interpreted on sub-metre imagery. The product attains 89% overall accuracy (95% CI $\pm 2\%$); producer's accuracies range from 77% (shrub/herbaceous vegetation) to 99% (water bodies), with user's accuracies >93% for agricultural strata. Confusions arise primarily between spectrally similar urban green spaces and semi-natural grasslands, and between early construction sites and bare soil. An overview and a schematic of the processing pipeline are provided (see Figure 1).

Three methodological insights follow. First, the current density and thematic granularity of OSM land-use tags suffice to train deep networks that generalize across

Shultz, Li, Wu, Weil, Auer & Zipf (2026). OSMLanduse: A Dataset of European Union Land Use at 10m Resolution Derived from OpenStreetMap and Sentinel-2

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diverse biogeographic regions without external annotation campaigns [4]. Second, multi-temporal medoid compositing coupled with per-country models dampens atmospheric noise and phenological divergence, enabling continental consistency from uncalibrated top-of-atmosphere data. Third, open-science practices—public code, permissive licenses, trained weights, and cloud execution—place 10 m land-use mapping within reach of resource-constrained institutions [5].

Compute and reproducibility: The end-to-end continental training required 96 GPU-hours on commodity instances on FAO SEPAL; this is a one-off cost. Inference or fine-tuning on new regions is substantially cheaper. We release trained weights and per-country recipes so groups can (i) reuse weights as-is, (ii) fine-tune where OSM density allows, or (iii) run regional subsets. The pipeline is tile-based and linear in area; data-scarce regions can start with inference-only mapping and selectively fine-tune.

Update cadence: We will publish periodic updates by reusing weights and re-training only tiles with substantial OSM deltas, refreshing Sentinel-2 composites accordingly; the code already supports snapshot replacement. This addresses OSM temporal asynchrony and supports incorporation of community edits into future releases [6].

Applications and limitations: The dataset enables analyses from peri-urban sprawl quantification (SDG 11.3.1) to biodiversity sampling frames and downscaling of economic statistics. Limitations persist: crowdsourced tags are asynchronous; spectral ambiguity endures in arid shrublands and gravel pits; features <10 m (e.g., hedgerows) are sub-pixel. By releasing not only the map but all scripts, configs, and weights, we facilitate replication, auditing, regional adaptation, and incremental updates [6].

Figure 1. Overview of OSMLanduse (EU28, 10m, Mar 2020) and processing pipeline schematic (OSM tag harmonization, Sentinel-2 medoid compositing, per-country ResNet classification, raster–vector fusion).

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Behaviour-Based Quality Assessment of OpenStreetMap Data in Data-Scarce Areas Using Unsupervised Machine Learning

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Despite the widespread use of OpenStreetMap (OSM) data, the quality of OSM data varies considerably across regions and contributors, especially in data-scarce urban areas like Dhaka. Traditional OSM quality assessments rely on extrinsic comparisons with satellite imagery or authoritative datasets, which are often unavailable in the very regions that need the data the most [1], [2]. To overcome this challenge, a reproducible, unsupervised machine learning framework is proposed to assess OSM data quality intrinsically, based on contributor behaviour metadata alone. Specifically, Dhaka—a data-scarce and fast-growing megacity in Bangladesh, selected as a study area—using the hypothesis that distinct contributor behavioural patterns correlate with different levels of data reliability. This behaviour-centric perspective leverages the insight that contributor frequency, recency, thematic focus, and spatial editing behaviour can serve as meaningful proxies for feature quality [3], [4]. Frequent and recent contributions from contributors with a strong thematic focus can assist in achieving higher tagging accuracy and lowering the risk of outdated data. Additionally, contributions that are spatially wide imply systematic, less erratic mapping.

Roads and buildings for Dhaka were extracted from an *.osm.pbf* file using the Pyrosm library. Then an enriched feature vector was created for each unique contributor based on their editing behaviour: *total_edits*, *edit_rate*, *active_days*, *spatial_extent*, *pct_road*, *pct_building*, *weekday_activity*, and *days_since_last_edit*. Temporal activity (frequency and recency), thematic preference (roads vs buildings), and spatial coverage are captured by these features. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) applies for dimensionality reduction and shows that PC1 roughly represents global mapping activity, while PC2 corresponds to thematic attention (road versus building), and PC3 represents the geographical coverage of contributions. These observations are supported by a feature contribution heatmap (Figure 1(a)), which indicates that it is reasonable to consider the behavioural features to be interpretable and highly separable in the component-reduced space. PCA also has the purpose of reducing noise and getting the data ready for clustering [5].

Next, an unsupervised machine learning model was applied in two phases: (1) dimensionality reduction with PCA and (2) clustering with KMeans (4) and HDBSCAN. K-means clustering (with $k = 4$) and HDBSCAN, a density-based clustering, are performed on

Ahmed, M. (2026). Behaviour-Based Quality Assessment of OpenStreetMap Data in Data-Scarce Areas Using Unsupervised Machine Learning

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the PCA-transformed feature set. The silhouette score of the K-Means model was 0.951, suggesting high cohesion within the clusters and good separation between the clusters of behaviours. The PCA cluster scatterplot (Figure 1(c)) indicates four separated clusters: (1) Most participants (Figure 1(b)) fall in cluster 0, which mainly encompasses casual or one-hit contributors who probably participate in sporadic mapathons or make large-scale imports, (2) Clusters 1 and 2 consist of moderate to heavy contributors, who are relatively more or less stable, with richer semantic tagging, and whose edits are spatially distributed. (3) Cluster 3 is composed of a small group of “power users”, who are characterised by high activity volume and a large geographical distribution.

HDBSCAN is also used on the same dataset in order to analyse its capability of separating various densities in clusters and noise. HDBSCAN found small, dense clusters and labelled a large percentage of contributors as noise. Although helpful for identifying anomalousness and potential vandalism, HDBSCAN was unable to produce as clear clusters for the main contributors as KMeans, likely because of the extreme imbalance in contributor engagement. This benchmarking demonstrated that K-Means comes with better interpretability and cluster stability and is therefore preferred for behavioural segmentation at the high volumes of the OSM dataset.

To further verify the clustering, the changes in edit volume over time per cluster were investigated, and feature distributions per cluster were calculated. The contributor distribution bar chart (Figure 1 (b)) shows that the participation structure in OSM is highly skewed, which is also in line with previous VGI studies [6, 7]. Feature analysis showed that clusters associated with more recent, frequent, and thematically rich editing were also responsible for higher-quality contributions—consistent with prior work linking contributor experience to data quality [3], [4], [8].

A key contribution of this work is its extensible and repeatable approach. All data processing, feature engineering, PCA and clustering have been performed in Python (Colab) with open-source packages (scikit-learn, geopandas, pyrosm, matplotlib). This method doesn't need any external validation databases, so it is particularly adapted for developing countries and isolated locations, where reference data are limited or unavailable [2].

This study contributes methodologically to three areas in the sciences, more precisely to the area of geospatial data science, unsupervised machine learning, and VGI quality assurance, in showing how user behaviour can be harnessed for deriving inherent data quality. It complements the literature about behaviour-based contributor profiling, incorporates dimensionality reduction to facilitate the interpretation of results, and is an argument against central quality assessment as well as one for local quality assessment, which seems feasible even in urban settings with complex mobility patterns.

Pragmatically, this work can help NGOs, local authorities and the OSM community to support the allocation of resources toward data validation and enrichment where coverage is primarily in lower-quality contribution clusters. It also allows hybrid-quality models with behaviour signals that are augmented with selective extrinsic checks (such as anomaly detection or community verification). For example, contributors from Cluster 3 (power users) may be assigned higher trust weights in quality models, while edits from Cluster 0 may be flagged for further review or enrichment.

In conclusion, a new behaviour-based quality assessment of the OSM report is based on the specific usage of unsupervised machine learning. This cluster- and PCA-driven

design is transparent and interpretable, and completely reproducible. It is a model that addresses the challenges of working in data-scarce urban areas, and it paves the way for behaviour-driven VGI quality models in the framework of urban resilience, infrastructure planning and humanitarian mapping. Future studies will incorporate spatial error measures and use this methodology with longitudinal OSM data for quality evolution monitoring.

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User Testing of AI-Assisted Mapping Tool fAIr

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Humanitarian organizations need maps for their activities. However, there is a lack of quality maps in many countries. The Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT) is coordinating a global effort for humanitarian mapping, where volunteers create maps of remote localities. They use satellite imagery to search for roads and buildings and draw them into the OpenStreetMap. Despite all the efforts of volunteers, many regions remain insufficiently mapped [1]. Artificial intelligence (AI) is already used to analyze satellite imagery. There is thus an opportunity to use AI for humanitarian mapping as well. HOT proposed the fAIr project (<https://fair.hotosm.org/>) – an open-source AI-assisted mapping tool [2]. In a presentation from SOTM 2024, Anna Zanchetta [3] analyzed the performance of fAIr in detecting buildings in different conditions.

Our group, located in the Department of Geography, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Czechia, is part of the humanitarian mapping community Missing Maps Czechia and Slovakia. We were in contact with the fAIr developers from HOT – Omran Najjar, Kshitij Sharma, and Anna Zanchetta. They asked us if we could organize user testing of the first version of fAIr. The goal was to compare AI-assisted mapping of buildings with the fAIr tool and classic manual mapping of buildings without AI assistance. The popular JOSM editor, which offers experienced tools for manual building mapping, was used for comparison.

The experiment took place in an online environment during November 2024. The experiment took place in four different sessions, so each participant could choose the day and time that suited them best. Training datasets were prepared for 24 different localities around the globe. The localities were divided into easy (14) and complex (10). Complex localities were characterized by a high density of buildings and poorer imagery quality. 26 participants took part in the experiment – 14 beginners and 12 experienced contributors (with more than 1000 buildings in OpenStreetMap mapped). The participants were divided into groups A and B, so there were similar numbers of experienced contributors and beginners in both groups.

Each participant was assigned one locality to map in fAIr and one locality to map in JOSM. One of the localities was easy and the other complex, so that a similar number of easy and complex localities were mapped in each editor. It was also ensured that beginners and experienced contributors mapped a similar number of easy and complex localities in both editors. The selection of a locality from easy localities and the selection of a locality from complex localities were random. It was possible for two participants to map the same complex locality because there were fewer of them. This did not affect the results, because the participants did not see each other's data.

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Each session was structured as follows:

- An explanation of the rules for correctly and incorrectly mapped buildings.
- 45 minutes: group A mapped in fAIr, group B mapped in JOSM
- 5 minutes: break
- 45 minutes: group B mapped in fAIr, group A mapped in JOSM
- Participants filled in the feedback questionnaire.

Validators evaluated the mapped buildings, and the results were analyzed. Efficiency (number of buildings mapped per minute), effectiveness (proportion of buildings mapped correctly), and satisfaction (feedback from participants) were analyzed. Mapping in JOSM (86.08 %) was significantly more accurate and faster (4.23 buildings/min) than the fAIr tool (78.22 % and 1.97 buildings/min).

Beginners mapped faster in JOSM (2.89 buildings/min) than in fAIr (2.08 buildings/min), but the mapping quality was almost the same in JOSM (79.28 %) and fAIr (80.41 %). Experienced contributors mapped much faster (5.69 buildings/min) and with higher quality (93.45 %) in JOSM than in fAIr (1.84 buildings/min and 75.38 %). Interestingly, it also means that beginners have better results of mapping quality (80.41%) and mapping speed in fAIr (2.08 buildings/min) than experienced contributors (75.38 % and 1.84 buildings/min). On the contrary, experienced contributors have much better results in mapping quality (93.45 %) and mapping speed (5.69 buildings/min) in JOSM than beginners (79.28 % and 2.89 buildings/min).

We also analyzed the influence of the complexity of mapping locality, e.g., the density of buildings in the mapped site and the quality of the imagery. For easy localities, experienced contributors generally have higher mapped building counts, indicating better fAIr performance on simpler tasks. For complex localities, the number of buildings mapped by experienced contributors drops significantly, suggesting that complex localities pose a challenge even for experienced contributors. A higher number of errors was found in complex localities, where AI likely generated lower-quality building outlines. Interestingly, for complex localities, beginners mapped more buildings than experienced contributors, which may suggest that they focus on quantity. This could indicate potential quality issues.

An example of data can be seen in Figure 1. In the JOSM editor, participants mapped building by building. In fAIr, buildings are mapped at larger distances. The reason is that participants selected only those buildings for which the AI model generated a high-quality outline, which is the correct procedure. In the case of fAIr, participants mapped practically only buildings with a simple shape. For buildings with a more complex shape, fAIr apparently failed to create a high-quality outline successfully.

Figure 1. Buildings mapped using the fAIr tool (green) and the JOSM editor (blue).

23 participants answered a mapping feedback questionnaire. They indicated that fAIr was not their preferred tool for mapping, but more than half of them said they would return to it. In their opinion, fAIr is suitable for beginners. Most participants stated that the buildings generated by AI need to be further modified and that correcting errors is difficult.

After evaluating the results and feedback from participants, recommendations were proposed for the further development of the fAIr tool:

- fAIr is a beginner-friendly tool. It is suitable for quick mapping of simple features. Users appreciated the simple interface. Beginners have similar results in fAIr as experienced contributors, sometimes even better. Users suggested combining both tools – starting with quick mapping in fAIr and refining the quality in JOSM.
- Participants had issues with AI-generated shapes, as fAIr did not allow proper mapping of more complex buildings. Often, separate buildings were mistakenly combined into a single outline. These problems were greater in the complex areas (e.g., density of the mapped site and the quality of the imagery), where the AI seemed unable to design good building outlines.
- The results were influenced by the fact that JOSM includes tools for mapping buildings, which gives it an advantage over fAIr. However, JOSM does not have specialized tools for mapping other features (e.g., roads). It is possible that mapping these features would yield more favorable results for fAIr.
- Users believe that fAIr has the potential to improve the mapping process and could be helpful if key problems are addressed.

Some problems will likely be solved using innovations in the new version of fAIr – e.g., using a YOLO-type ML model and increasing the speed of prediction of building outlines [2]. A logical continuation of our study would be to repeat user testing with the new version of fAIr – e.g., compare the results of the RAMP model from the original version of fAIr with the YOLO model from the latest version in the same locality. We want to not only scientifically test the new version of fAIr, but also use it during the autumn at one of the mapathons we organize in the Missing Maps Czechia and Slovakia. Ideally, fAIr would be used at a mapathon that will be attended mainly by contributors with experience in using AI, e.g., employees of IT companies.

The results of the experiment were published as a public scientific report [4]: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/10I1wz1BHsBXmBjXMx99KzqBwaVpj5MJN/view?usp=sharing>.

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What opinions do LLMs/chatbots have about OpenStreetMap?

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Large Language Models (LLMs) are pretrained on vast amounts of human data and it is reasonable to assume that LLMs can reflect the AOVs (Attitudes, Opinions and Values) embedded in the data [1]. LLMs are increasingly being used in open-ended contexts, where the opinions they reflect in response to subjective queries can have a profound impact on shaping the views of society at large [2]. LLMs/chatbots can be prompted to generate opinion-like text. For example, in Malleson et. al [3] LLMs are used to give opinions on neighbourhood change. The huge popularity of these chatbots means that opinionated text produced by LLMs/chatbots can have the potential to be very influential on the user [4,5]. When LLMs are integrated into search engines, social platforms, and other interactive systems, their outputs when the user is seeking opinions or viewpoints can become a user's first—or only—exposure to a topic [5]. We have concerns around how LLMs can shape how OpenStreetMap (OSM) is used in the future and therefore our work aims to understand potential biases or negative opinions produced by LLMs/chatbots when learning about OSM. We investigate the opinions or views expressed by some of the major current LLMs when prompted or questioned about their opinions on specific aspects of OSM. We make the assumption that LLMs will have been trained on data and information related to OSM and in particular legacy topics such as: data quality, comparison with official or authoritative sources, accuracy, bias in crowdsourced data, and so on. Our research question asks: can we quantitatively and qualitatively understand the AOVs of LLMs around topics related to OSM? To the best of our knowledge, there is no research currently reported about this topic. The majority of work published about LLMs and OSM revolves around using the LLMs as mapping assistants [6,7] or using LLMs to enrich existing data or allow more accessible approaches to mapping [8]. Other works have considered the ability of chatbots such as ChatGPT to take a GIS exam [9], exploit the deep contextual understandings in LLMs for building function classification in OSM [10], or enhance accessibility to GIS using AI (as in [9]). Our work steps back from this by investigating how LLMs/chatbots can be influential in informing opinions about crowdsourced geospatial data and its usage within GIS applications and research. We do this by instructing LLMs to perform two tasks related to the following topics: geospatial data quality, temporal currency of OSM data and overall sentiment towards OSM.

Each topic of inquiry consisted of a qualitative and a quantitative task. Prompts were designed to elicit structured outputs in JSON format which ensures consistency across

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responses. Models were queried through the University of Florida NaviGator Chat interface [11], which is a customized version of the open-source Open WebUI [12] enabling calls to multiple chatbots hosted on different backends. We tested different variants of commonly used LLMs/chatbots, including Gemini (Google), GPT (OpenAI), Mistral (Mistral AI), Llama (Meta), Claude (Anthropic) and Nova (Amazon). UF NaviGator Chat allowed uniform control of generation parameters (*random seed=123, temperature=0, top_p=0.00000001*) that ultimately ensured that responses were as deterministic as possible, unaffected by different configurations of commercial chat interfaces. Additionally, the same system prompt was used for each task to establish a consistent framing, and a new session was started for each task. An additional prominent chatbot, Grok-4 (xAI) was also included, but queried separately through its web interface due to platform constraints. Responses were collected as JSON documents and subsequently parsed into spreadsheets. For the qualitative tasks, themes were manually identified from chatbot explanations and reasons, and synthesized into summary categories. For quantitative tasks, numerical outputs were aggregated. All chatbot versions, prompts, system settings and raw responses are available as Supplementary Material for transparency and reproducibility. Given the volume of results generated, for brevity, we focus on the following aspects of the tasks: the quality of OSM, the temporal currency of OSM, and the overall sentiment towards OSM shown by the LLMs/chatbots.

The quality of OSM: 12 out of 15 chatbots responded “Yes” to the question whether OSM is a high quality source of geospatial data, which suggests that generally LLMs/chatbots recognize the value of OSM. The main reason supporting high quality was the OSM community that continuously contributes, maintains, and verifies data, leading to high levels of detail, coverage, and frequent updates. This theme was mentioned 9 times. Other top reasons that emerged were the open-source nature and free availability of OSM data that encourages continuous improvement, verification, collaboration, and widespread use by a diverse range of users, and transparency it fosters (8 times), and the robust systems for quality control and assurance (5 times). Among reasons questioning OSM’s high quality, the community approach emerged with a different sentiment: the heavy reliance on volunteers leading to inconsistencies. Other reasons mainly highlighted potential accuracy and quality issues, also supported by the lack of professional-grade surveying tools available to contributors. The models also rated OSM on 5 dimensions of geospatial data quality using a scale from 1 (Very Low) to 5 (Very High). The quantitative ratings indicate that OSM is perceived by chatbots as strong in temporal quality (avg=3.93, SD=0.8), while completeness (avg=3.33, SD=0.62) emerged as the most variable dimension, reflecting regional disparities in data coverage. Other data dimensions such as positional accuracy (avg=3.73, SD=0.59), logical consistency (avg=3.6, SD=0.63) and thematic accuracy (avg=3.53, SD=0.52) received comparable ratings, that suggests that none of the probed data quality dimensions are considered outstandingly low or high by the chatbots.

Temporal currency of OSM: When asked whether OSM is up-to-date compared to other leading providers of geospatial data, chatbots present a mixed picture with 7 responding “Yes” and 8 responding “No”. This indicates that chatbots lean towards slight skepticism about OSM’s currency relative to proprietary and authoritative sources. Top themes supporting high temporal currency were rapid updates facilitated by a large and active community and near real-time edits and corrections, often within minutes or hours. The chatbots answering yes generally recognized the crowdsourced model that can often

reflect on-the-ground changes more quickly than the scheduled update cycles of commercial providers. Other common themes were local knowledge that is more adept at mapping hyperlocal and informal features, as well as the open nature of OSM, encompassing open source software, open data and the editable, wiki-style model that allows anyone to contribute without commercial and proprietary restrictions constraining the framework. The main reasons questioning whether OSM is up-to-date were inconsistencies and the commercial advantage of other map providers. Inconsistencies were mentioned both related to the volunteer community and correspondingly the geographical inconsistency in areas with minimal volunteer presence. The commercial advantage was highlighted both in terms of resources available to commercial providers (e.g. dedicated teams, automated services) as well as the data sources they can utilize for generating geospatial data (satellite imagery, systematic data collection). The quantitative ratings reinforce this mixed picture. Chatbots were prompted to rate the typical update speed of OSM compared to major commercial providers for different feature types on a 5-point scale (1=much slower, 5=much faster). New Points of Interests (POIs) were rated the highest (avg=4.0, SD=1.0), indicating that OSM is generally faster at reflecting newly opened business, amenities or landmarks. New residential streets (avg=3.13, SD=1.19) and major highway changes (avg=3.0, SD=0.76) also scored reasonably well, which again suggests that OSM is often comparable or faster than commercial providers for important changes in the transportation network. By contrast, OSM tends to lag in more resource-intensive or systematically mapped categories: building footprints in urban areas (avg=2.73, SD=0.7), and especially land use changes in rural areas (avg=1.73, SD=0.7), where OSM is generally slower or much slower than commercial datasets.

Overall sentiment towards OSM: When asked to provide keywords that capture the main advantages and disadvantages of OSM, chatbots emphasized its global coverage, community-driven nature and the fact that it is free and customizable. These qualities collectively highlight OSM's value proposition as a crowdsourced, open and cost-free alternative to commercial providers. Other frequently mentioned strengths include OSM's reputation for being up-to-date, its open-source ecosystem as well as its potential for frequent updates and rich local details in areas with active contributors. The most common disadvantages reflect concerns about inconsistent quality, volunteer dependency and incomplete or variable coverage with gaps and risk of vandalism or errors. Several responses also pointed to a steep learning curve and potential technical barriers that may limit adoption among less experienced users, as well as the lack of official support or validation that commercial providers can guarantee. Despite the challenges, the overall sentiment towards OSM tends to be strongly positive. On a scale from -10 (overwhelmingly negative) to +10 (overwhelmingly positive), the average rating across 15 LLMs/chatbots was +7.07, which indicates that OSM is widely regarded as a valuable, reliable and innovative geospatial resource.

Overall, from our initial experimentation it appears that LLMs/chatbots do positively recognize the value of OSM. While it is not possible to discuss all of the results generated, it is recognised that the OSM community continuously contributes, has local knowledge, reflects on-the-ground changes, maintains, and verifies data, and this contributes to high levels of detail, coverage, etc. However, the OSM ecosystem that relies on volunteers can also lead to inconsistencies in these areas. Quantitatively, the LLMs/chatbots queried had no strong opinions either way on temporal quality, completeness, positional accuracy, etc.

Our results suggest that the sentiment towards OSM from the LLMs/chatbots queried is strongly positive and this indicates that OSM is widely regarded as a valuable, reliable and innovative geospatial resource. This positive sentiment can have a positive influence on users using LLMs/chatbots to explore OSM or evaluate OSM's suitability for a specific task. The primary limitation of this experiment is that LLMs lack genuine opinions as their outputs are statistical reflections of their training data. Methodologically, our use of structured prompts and deterministic parameters ensured reproducibility but constrained responses to a single, probable output, not exploring the models' full generative variability. Details about the included models, experimental setup as well as the data supporting these results are available at <https://osf.io/wc25k/>. There are some immediate considerations for future work. These include assessing the overall model size, measuring the consistency of outputs generated from the queried LLMs/chatbots, and potentially surveying human subjects about OSM in the same way as the LLMs/chatbots are queried for this work.

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PlaceCrafter: Curating Urban Functional Regions through Platial Clustering of OpenStreetMap Points of Interest

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The world is not just made of streets, buildings, and zones; it is shaped by how people engage and interact with places in their everyday lives. This manuscript presents a web-based geospatial tool that enables the mapping of these lived places and locales named PlaceCrafter. PlaceCrafter supports researchers in identifying platial regions: functional, human-centred areas that cross administrative and formal boundaries. The framework is built on OpenStreetMap, combining (near) real-time clustering, analysis, and statistical validation of these platial regions. PlaceCrafter is an initial demonstration for exploring the subjective experiences of place through existing datasets and city structures.

Contemporary urban analysis requires tools and analytical software that can not only capture the physical structure of the city, but also the dynamic and human-centred places that can emerge from everyday interactions. While these technologies, such as existing OpenStreetMap (OSM) [1] views and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) [2] are effective for spatial tasks, these abstractions fail to understand the notions of place when compared to space [3]. Recent work [4, 5] has sought to shift the focus towards platial information systems, tools which situate the human experience, subjective knowledge, and fuzzy representation as a comparison to existing spatial systems. These fuzzy, subjective, and personal representations attempt to model 'place' as a contrast to space.

PlaceCrafter responds to this challenge by integrating a spatial-platial [6] approach to identifying regions that are functionally cohesive, representing dense and meaningful concentrations of specific points of interest (POI). The POIs are traditional representations of space within GIS [3], such as cafes, museums, and places of worship. Rather than relying on the top-down designation of locations, PlaceCrafter supports researchers in curating clusters that represent how space is used as opposed to administratively divided. Aligning with recent calls in GIScience to shift from 'space' to 'place' in smart city analysis [7] and building on work which has operationalised the sense of place in urban contexts [8].

PlaceCrafter is designed not just to analyse space, but to make its platial structure visible, explorable, and comprehensible to analysts, researchers, and planners. While PlaceCrafter captures place through functional coherence of POIs, it does not yet capture

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temporal or subjective meanings that also shape lived experiences. Figure 1 presents the web-based application, developed in TypeScript using React, Vite, Leaflet, Turf.js, and D3.js. The software uses the Overpass API [9] to retrieve (near, depending on number of POIs loaded) real-time user-filtered POI data. The datasets are organised into categories based upon the existing OSM semantic structures [10]; these filters can be customised depending on the analytical task. This functionality supports the purpose of the framework, which is to enable researchers to understand city form and structure through a platial lens.

Figure 1. Screenshot of PlaceCrafter set around the Nottingham city centre, clustering places based on tourism, historical, leisure, and natural categories within the city.

PlaceCrafter is structured around four phases guided by the OSM filtering approach: the initial phase (1) focuses on filtering and selection of relevant OSM categories [10], building upon existing work, such as POI Pulse [11] which classifies regions using semantic signatures, and user behaviour to generate profiles of locations in the Los Angeles area and ClusterRadar [12] which supports comparative spatial clustering and parameter tuning through interactive visualisation to examine how clusters change temporally; the second phase (2) is where the fuzzy clustering approaches are applied interactively to the selected category grouping and includes user-selectable K-Means [13] for compact formations, DBSCAN [14] for spatial structures, and hierarchical clustering for multi-level structures. These methods are applied to the grouped and filtered POI data to reveal dynamic regions.

The penultimate phase (3) focuses on statistical validation, where each clustered region is evaluated using established spatial metrics. These evaluations include the nearest neighbour index to assess spatial clustering, silhouette scores [15] for understanding cluster coherence, and spatial autocorrelation is measured using a simplified Moran's I statistic for insights into category-based dependency [16]; The final phase is (4) visualisation, which explores the concept of platial readability, where each region is presented not just spatially but semantically, with data supported by POI type, diversity score, and density metrics. Additionally, the platial visualisation techniques used support the emerging approaches to conveying ambiguity, overlap, and functional gradients [3, 17]. The visualisation subsystem is modular for end-user requirements, supporting fuzzy spray can visualisation and region

influence grids, convex hulls, kernel density heatmaps, and region quality indicators.

Figure 1 presents a case study using PlaceCrafter to analyse Nottingham, United Kingdom and the surrounding areas. The POI filtering focused on tourism, historical, leisure, and natural categories. A total of 534 POIs were clustered into 18 functional regions using K-Means. There were 344 historical POIs and 111 leisure POIs as the largest categories from the filtering. The spatial pattern reflects the diverse landscape of Nottingham, with dense clusters in the city centre based around historical POIs, with suburban and rural areas having a more diffuse pattern of historic and leisure clustering. The statistical validation showed strong autocorrelation using Moran's I (0.68) and a high internal cohesion Silhouette score (0.83), confirming the utility of platial clustering in capturing real-world functional structures.

PlaceCrafter offers a powerful and emerging way to engage with spatial data, but its outputs are shaped by the characteristics of OSM. The crowd-sourced nature of this data means that those tied to commerce or tourism are more visible than the informal or everyday categories related to subjective personal experiences. However, previous research has shown that OSM data is generally reliable for urban-area analysis, despite some noise [18]. The clustering algorithms respond to spatial density and POI tag semantics, which do not explicitly capture human-perceived understandings of place boundaries, indicating a need for inclusion of social media data such as those used in POI Pulse [11] or the subjective experiences captured from linked walking narratives in WalkGIS [19].

The software and framework is being developed to be an open-source software which enables broader use, adaptation, and academic contributions in platial information systems. Planned expansions include supporting historical analysis to track the evolution of platial regions and their changes over time. We intend to further expand the platform to incorporate multi-comparative views of platial functional regions, enabling cities, timeframes, and thematic domains to be compared in real-time. We also intend to conduct a qualitative study investigating how users, analysts, and researchers interpret and engage with PlaceCrafter's outputs in practice. These improvements will help the validation of the tool's interpretability and role as a flexible analytical environment for platial analysis.

As cities continue to change, we hope to explore how PlaceCrafter can be used to understand engagement as increasingly layered and complex. Recognising that cities are more than their administrative boundaries, while valuing the role of spatial data, PlaceCrafter helps uncover the functional geography of place by clustering OSM POIs into meaningful regions that reflect how place is used, shared, and shaped through the spatial logic embedded in mapped data. The practical implications of this work include informing the design of walking routes or geo-narratives in more dynamic and context-sensitive ways.

The PlaceCrafter source code is available as open-source software on GitHub at <https://github.com/jwilliamsresearch/PlaceCrafter>. All point of interest data is sourced from OpenStreetMap (<https://openstreetmap.org>) and accessed via the Overpass API (<https://overpass-api.de>) under the Open Database License.

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Leveraging OpenStreetMap for Hyperlocal Geocoding of Twitter Data: A Spatiotemporal Analysis of the 2016 Haifa (Israel) Wildfire

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The increasing frequency and severity of urban wildfires demand new sources of near real-time information to support emergency response and disaster risk reduction [1-4]. In this study, we present an application for extracting and georeferencing the spatiotemporal distribution of tweets associated with the November 2016 wildfire in Haifa, Israel. The unprecedented urban fire influenced densely populated neighborhoods, caused extensive infrastructural damage, and led to the evacuation of thousands of residents [5]. However, because of the nature and extent of the fire that lasted nearly 3 days, complete and reliable information concerning the emergence and development of new fire locations at the sub-city scale was only partial. Accordingly, management and decision-making procedures were complicated and some of the cascading events along with the occurrence of the catastrophe were hard to detect and addressed.

The purpose of the study was to analyze tweets as a potential source of near real-time information and examine to what degree Twitter can be used to assist decision-making during occurrences of urban catastrophes. The implemented research combined Natural Language Processing (NLP), Machine Learning (ML), and Geographic Information Science (GIScience) to filter, classify, and precisely geolocate tweets at the city, neighborhood or street-level resolution [6]. One of the main components of the established geospatial framework was OpenStreetMap (OSM) used in conjunction with the GeoNames gazetteer to construct a comprehensive spatial reference corpus. This enabled the geocoding of both explicitly and implicitly localized tweets that lack GPS metadata—an essential challenge given that only 1–3% of the tweets are geotagged with reliable geographic coordinates [7, 8].

We have purchased approximately 2.4 million tweets using keywords related to the wildfire (in the Hebrew, Arabic, and English languages) between November 24th –27th, 2016. After classification using topic modelling and RCNN (Recurrent Convolutional Neural

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Networks) [9], around 114,000 tweets were labelled as relevant to the event. Of these, only 31 tweets were geotagged with geographic coordinates which is obviously an insufficient number of observations to perform spatial analysis. To overcome this shortcoming, we implemented a text-based georeferencing approach leveraging gazetteer data extracted from the OpenStreetMap and GeoNames databases. Accordingly, we converted 18 OSM shapefiles into a unified point dataset containing a wide variety of geographic features—ranging from neighborhoods and roads to public buildings and natural landmarks. This dataset was merged with a version of the GeoNames corpus to create a point-based localized gazetteer representing the Haifa metropolitan area and its environs. For the purpose of geocoding, each point was associated with its place name in Hebrew, Arabic, or English. Following, the geocoding pipeline consisted of the following key steps: (1) NLP techniques including tokenization, stemming, and stop-word removal to extract named entities and spatial references from the tweet’s metadata [10]; (2) FuzzyWuzzy-based string matching algorithm that computes the Levenshtein distances between strings extracted from the tweet tokens and the place names in our gazetteer [11]; and (3) matchings were assigned a confidence score, which allowed us to weight the credibility and accuracy of the spatial data. For example, georeferenced tweets with scores above 90% were deemed highly reliable for trend detection.

The process yielded 16,672 georeferenced tweets distributed across 130 unique localities within Haifa and its close vicinity. To examine whether these locations of tweets represent fire hotspots, we added the official reported fire incidents by the Israel Fire and Rescue Services (IFRS) [12]. The geographic distributions of the georeferenced tweets as well as the IFRS data are presented in [13], accompanied with an online map [14]. Following, we conducted a spatiotemporal inspection by aggregating tweets into 5×5 km grid cells and 8-hour intervals—bins that were informed by the density of localities extracted from the OSM/GeoNames hybrid gazetteer. We used ESRI ArcGIS Pro to generate Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) maps [15] and 3D visualizations of the tweets’ distribution. The 2D and 3D densities were then superimposed on the real IFRS data resulting in strong temporal and spatial correspondence. In most of the bins where actual fires were documented, relevant georeferenced tweets were also present. Additionally, tweets often captured the cascading nature of the fire, spreading across Haifa and adjacent towns. Importantly, the spatial granularity enabled us to detect not only urban hotspots but also peripheral areas such as the cities of Daliyat el-Carmel and Akko, which were underrepresented in the media reporting.

Figure 1. (a) the spatial distribution of grid-Cells in Haifa and environs; (b) Spatiotemporal distribution of georeferencing accuracy scores (results of Levenshtein distance algorithm used for token-locality matching) achieved to georeference tweets, ranging 0-90 and 99–100; (c) spatiotemporal distribution of aggregated tweets into separate 8-hour bins.

OpenStreetMap played a pivotal role in our ability to extract high-resolution geospatial insights from unstructured social media content. Its richness and multilingual tagging schema allowed effective token matching across Hebrew, Arabic, and English tweets. While GeoNames provided broad administrative and populated place names, OSM uniquely offered sub-city level details such as parks, fire stations, neighborhoods, and points of interest—that dramatically enhanced geocoding precision. The findings of the study demonstrate that OSM and GeoNames might function as an open, extensible backbone for disaster informatics, particularly in regions where official geospatial datasets are sparse or restricted. Additionally, this research showcases a replicable model for fusing crowd-sourced geographic data with user-generated content (e.g., Twitter) to inform emergency responses at the hyperlocal scale. It is worth mentioning that since the conduction of the study, Twitter (X) has switched ownership and accordingly services it used to provide are prone to changes. Nevertheless, the study demonstrates principles and best practices of how crowd-sourced geographic data in conjunction with social media data might assist in acquiring near-real time information during crisis management.

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Open Mapping for Urban Resilience: A Routing Model to Nearest Safe Spaces in Earthquake-Vulnerable Dhaka

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Dhaka, a rapidly expanding megacity with extreme seismic vulnerability, sits near active fault lines and has grown by tens of millions in recent decades without sufficient disaster planning [1]. With 15–20 million residents and dense informal settlements, little per-capita open ground exists. This study maps all candidate “safe spaces” (parks, plazas, empty lots, schoolyards, etc.) and computes routes to the nearest one for every neighborhood, using only open data and free GIS tools. To ensure scientific validity, the study grounds the methodology in recent literature: for example, Fan et al. highlight that mapping urban open space (UOS) at high resolution can improve disaster emergency response [2], and Messina et al. show that volunteer mapping completeness varies widely in dense slums [3]. The approach integrates these insights: it uses satellite imagery and existing data to classify open land, leverages OpenStreetMap (OSM) for city features while addressing its gaps with community field mapping, and implements routing in QGIS (open-source) to maximize reproducibility. The result is a set of open-data maps and tools that urban planners, NGOs, and citizens can use for earthquake preparedness.

The open space identification begins with multi-source imagery and GIS analysis using GEE (Google Earth Engine). The study first gathered Sentinel-2 and other recent satellite data plus available cadastral or land-use maps to spot candidate open areas. Using supervised classification (Random Forest on NDVI and texture bands) open-land patches were delineated. Existing open-space tags from OSM (e.g., *leisure=park*, *landuse=grass*) were imported as seed areas. Raw candidates were filtered by size and accessibility, and each candidate open space was verified via high-resolution imagery or site visits to ensure accessibility and safety. This two-step classification–verification process parallels best practices in remote-sensing UOS (Urban Open Space) mapping [2] and ensures reliability.

Because this work relies on OSM data for Dhaka’s roads and buildings, handling data gaps is vital. OSM in South Asia is known to be incomplete: a global study found that 69% of cities had <20% building coverage, and South Asian cities averaged ~9% completeness [4]. But for Dhaka, the capital of Bangladesh, the risk of a data gap is low due to the active role

of the OSM volunteers. Figure 1 illustrates the process of identifying candidate open spaces prior to routing analysis.

Figure 1. Identification of Open Space.

For routing to the nearest safe space, proprietary QGIS tools were used for a fully open-source workflow. The updated OSM road network was loaded into QGIS, and a routable graph was built in PostgreSQL with PostGIS and pgRouting. Alternatively, QNEAT3 in QGIS was used for shortest-path and isochrone algorithms [5]. The model calculates the shortest walking routes from populated centroids to the closest verified safe space, creating an accessibility map. Using QGIS/QNEAT3 removes licensing barriers and ensures replicability [6].

To assess the performance of the routing model, generated routes were cross-checked against high-resolution imagery and field-verified paths where available. Route lengths and travel times were compared across algorithms (pgRouting vs. QNEAT3) to ensure consistency, while accessibility scores were validated against known population centers. This verification step demonstrates that the model produces realistic routes and enhances confidence in its applicability for evacuation planning.

Replicability is prioritized, the workflow and parameters are documented, and all source data will be open after publication. The method could be repeated in any other Global South city by replacing input data with local OSM extracts and imagery. As Howe and Tullis

argue, publishing open-source GIS workflows enables reproducibility without software cost barriers [6].

Outputs include, (a) a map layer of all safe open spaces with attributes; (b) a model that will generate the route maps from each neighborhood to its nearest safe space. This model allows city planners, emergency responders, and community groups to explore evacuation scenarios.

This work is grounded in literature emphasizing that accessible open spaces reduce earthquake casualties [2], and that community-driven geospatial data are critical in informal cities [3]. The method aligns with SDG 11.7 on public open spaces. Best practices in participatory GIS stress empowering locals to map hazards and resources [7]. Recent reviews highlight that volunteer mapping increasingly fills data gaps when combined with local expertise [3]. This study contributes by adding disaster-relevant features to OSM and demonstrating a template for organized mapping campaigns in risk zones.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates how open geospatial science and community engagement can improve urban disaster resilience. The routing model is a bridge between science and practice, showing that open data and open tools together can overcome resource gaps in Global South cities. Governments and citizens gain reliable maps and decision-support tools at no extra cost, contributing to both the OSM community and disaster preparedness.

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When Metadata Isn't Enough: Extrinsic Quality Assessment of OSM Tags Using Custom Reference Data

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OpenStreetMap is a notable example of a database created by volunteers. Due to its open approach to data collection, establishing trust in the data is essential. Three key factors must be considered to evaluate this trust: completeness, correctness, and positional accuracy. The most common method in recent years for assessing large datasets like OpenStreetMap is to examine intrinsic data quality [1-3], which relies on metadata. However, this approach does not allow for a thorough analysis of the mapped features, resulting in only a rough estimate of the data's trustworthiness. To provide a more detailed understanding of the data, extrinsic data quality is evaluated by comparing OpenStreetMap with a reference dataset. This method is effective for evaluating feature completeness. However, when assessing attribute accuracy, a similarly detailed dataset for comparison is often unavailable. In these instances, the evaluator must gather their own reference dataset, which can be expensive and time-consuming. Because of that, previous studies and tools mainly focused on assessing attribute accuracy by utilizing intrinsic data quality [2, 4, 5].

In our study, we focused on assessing the extrinsic data quality of the city of Brno in the Czech Republic. We wanted to know how much we can trust OpenStreetMap tags (hereinafter referenced as attributes) in our city, and if there is some correlation between attribute accuracy and metadata of the features. A secondary objective was to determine how well ISO 19157 [6] can be used to assess the attribute quality of the OpenStreetMap. We chose the city's ten most mapped amenity features and gathered a reference dataset for these features. Since we knew what we would be evaluating, we have acquired a dataset perfect for evaluating OpenStreetMap. Thus, there was no need for major compromises in data evaluation. Over the course of several months, we traveled more than 1,000 km on foot and gathered a few thousand reference features using the Locus GIS app. Each feature contained a list of evaluated attributes together with a photo of the object for further evaluation. Evaluated amenities were *bench*, *waste_basket*, *recycling*, *restaurant*, *bicycle_parking*, *cafe*, *vending_machine*, *post_box*, *pub* and *fast_food* – the most mapped node features in Brno. The OpenStreetMap database was evaluated as of September 27, 2023.

Our assessment of OpenStreetMap's attribute accuracy revealed generally positive results. Several attributes in our sample achieved 100% accuracy, particularly those with boolean values. However, the most significant issues arose with string attributes that lack

defined value lists, such as *opening_hours*. Ultimately, the primary concern identified was the completeness of the data. We found that the completeness of feature occurrence is inadequate; we were only able to match 34.94% of all reference features with those in OpenStreetMap. This completeness varied significantly across evaluated amenities, with *waste_baskets* and *benches* being notably underrepresented. Incompleteness also affects the usability of attributes. Of the 72 tags evaluated, only 37 tags had at least 50% of their values filled in, and only 11 tags had over 90% of their values filled in.

We also assessed the positional accuracy of the data. Each amenity was evaluated separately, revealing average positional errors ranging from 2.63 meters to 4.02 meters. The median error was found to be between 1.83 meters and 3.13 meters. Overall, OpenStreetMap appears to be a relatively accurate positional database for the city of Brno, despite some isolated deviations (outliers).

When examining the relationship between attribute accuracy and feature metadata, we assumed that more users editing a feature would lead to more accurate data. This concept is known as the “many eyes principle” [7, 8]. However, the correlations between metadata (such as the number of contributors, versions, and days since the last edit) and attribute correctness are typically not statistically significant. As a result, no explicit dependency can be determined, and no clear patterns emerge from a few statistically significant values.

Our work also shows that evaluating OpenStreetMap using ISO 19157 [6] can be problematic because this standard does not consider multiple correct values or the varying degrees of attribute correctness (“level of detail” of attributes). Additionally, automating the evaluation of specific attributes, such as *opening_hours*, is challenging since these attributes can contain different yet correct values. Moreover, missing or incomplete documentation can significantly impact evaluations, as there should be clear rules specifying which values are considered correct. This presents a challenge for projects that follow the folksonomy principle, which encourages users to create new values that are often undocumented.

While ISO 19157 [6] includes the data quality element known as Quantitative Attribute Accuracy, it lacks a corresponding metric for non-quantitative attributes. This gap suggests a need for a new metric to assess the accuracy of non-quantitative values. However, such a metric should not be integrated into ISO 19157 [6] due to its specific focus. Instead, it should be included in guidelines designed specifically for evaluating OpenStreetMap or folksonomy in general. This approach would allow for better differentiation of situations like *payment:*=**, where the value *only* is correct, yet *yes* might also be considered correct, though with a lower degree of accuracy. Similarly, *outdoor_seating=patio* offers more precise information compared to *outdoor_seating=yes*. Currently, these subtle differences in attribute values cannot be effectively distinguished or described using the data quality elements found in ISO 19157 [6].

OpenStreetMap offers a comprehensive database, but its data quality varies significantly depending on the main tag and geometry type. In our sample data, both attribute and positional accuracy are reasonably good. However, a more significant issue is incompleteness, which includes missing and poorly mapped features and attributes. It is important to note that only a small subset of the database has been evaluated. The overall accuracy and completeness can vary significantly around the world, as demonstrated by numerous studies [9, 2, 10, 11]. This research aimed to evaluate the area of Brno while also exploring how ISO 19157 [6] can be used to assess OpenStreetMap. Yet, it seems that ISO

19157 can not be fully utilized for assessing folksonomy attributes. On the other hand, there is no problem with evaluating metrics like positional accuracy. Comparing Brno with a rural area or a similarly sized city in another country would yield valuable insights. However, this type of evaluation is very time-consuming due to the demands of data collection and processing. It is unlikely that a similar analysis could be conducted over a larger area, as it would require substantial resources. Nonetheless, this smaller-scale analysis offers important insights into the quality of OpenStreetMap data. The uniqueness of this study is underscored by the fact that similar research efforts focusing specifically on attribute evaluation in OpenStreetMap have not yet been conducted, mainly because of the demanding data collection. Previous studies have primarily focused on intrinsic data quality evaluations [1-5] or employed reference datasets that are not fully suitable for assessing attributes within OpenStreetMap [12].

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EUthMappers - Learning by Teaching Mapping

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EUthMappers is an ERASMUS+ initiative that promotes STEAM education in secondary schools throughout the European Union, enhancing students' digital skills and fostering environmental civic engagement [1]. The project fa. The idea is to establish an European mapping network similar to YouthMappers. This presentation outlines the project's implementation steps and showcases the remarkable results achieved by participating students.

The study aims to explore the possibility of integrating mapping as a necessary STEAM subject to engage students in exploring their surroundings and applying learning skills to contribute to humanitarian projects remotely. This research goal is then broken down into three smaller components that correspond to three phases of the project: creating accessible educational materials for students, guiding students to map their local environments, and participating in global humanitarian projects.

The project involves three universities (Politecnico di Milano, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, and Presovska Univerzita V Presov) and five secondary schools located in Italy, Spain, Slovakia, Romania, and Portugal, engaging approximately 160 students in total. The management of the project is done by Euronike, which is an association expert in capacity building activities and EU policies. Until now, the project has been running for two years, and was implemented in three phases.

- (1) Development of training materials: a comprehensive training package on open geospatial tools and data analysis was written and made available in six languages (English, Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, Slovakian and Romanian) [2]. This training was first delivered to teachers, who then transferred the knowledge to their students.
- (2) Local mapping projects: under the guidance of their teachers and with university collaboration, students developed local mapping initiatives from ideation to implementation, focusing on data acquisition and visualization techniques [3]. Across five European cities, students carried out mapping-focused projects that combined local engagement with practical outcomes. In Rovereto (Italy), students identified drainage channels on forest roads in the "Bosco della Città" as a central issue and mapped them using GPS and drone imagery. Since such features had

never been mapped on OSM, they engaged with the OSM community to propose and share a new mapping methodology. The resulting maps and database now support both routine and extraordinary maintenance by the Rovereto Forestry Service, helping mitigate hydrogeological risks. In Madrid (Spain), students mapped key elements related to mobility, leisure spaces, and climate shelters in the Arganzuela neighborhood. Working in groups, they identified and analyzed public space features, and then proposed concrete improvements to enhance young people's quality of life, which they presented at local events and forums. In Prešov (Slovakia), students focused on tree mapping in central city parks. After ecological training, they collected detailed data—such as species, trunk width, and height—using practical tools and mobile apps. Their results contributed to urban ecological databases and were showcased to the public during their school's open-door day. In Lisbon (Portugal), students explored how graffiti and street art reflect local identity by mapping urban artworks around their school. Through documentation and critical analysis, they created a record of artistic interventions with social and historical value, culminating in a community event promoting dialogue on youth expression in public space. In Pitești (Romania), students diagnosed low public awareness of recycling facilities and mapped the location, accessibility, and types of waste accepted at collection points. Their interactive map aimed to make recycling easier and more visible, encouraging environmental responsibility across the city. All the data obtained by students is contributed to the OSM platform. These projects show how students-led mapping activities can generate innovative tools, influence local planning, and foster active citizenship.

- (3) Humanitarian mapping collaboration: as the final activity, students participated in a humanitarian mapping project issued by the United Nations Global Service Centre (UNGSC). There were two workshops about humanitarian mapping and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in order to provide students basic knowledge about humanitarian mapping and their contribution to common goods [4,5]. Students are then trained on humanitarian mapping simulation projects before actually participating in a real-world scenario proposed by UN Maps, a programme in UNGSC to enhance UN peacekeeping missions operational capabilities through open geospatial information. The training project on OSM Sandbox took place in Idlib refugee camps in Syria (Figure 1), while during the actual project students map building data to contribute to generate a three-dimensional digital replica of the city Kandahar, Afghanistan [6]. The generated graphical replica can be used by the UNAMA mission engaging in Virtual Reality (VR) applications to train peacekeeping officers and as a collaborative tool for security and operational briefings. This final phase expanded students' collaborative abilities beyond their classrooms to engage in a meaningful humanitarian project with international impact.

EuthMappers project 27 contributions diagram

Figure 1. Contributions by the students throughout training phases in mapping buildings in Idlib refugee camps, Idlib, Syria.

Throughout these activities, students developed teamwork capabilities, creative thinking skills, and innovative data collection methodologies. Not to mention that, the project's partners also had to think outside the box so as to deliver complicated insights particularly geospatial technology, OSM, collaborative and humanitarian mapping, to the students in the most intuitive way possible. These results would then be demonstrated in two primary aspects, including: (A) statistics and data visualization of student mapping results, and (B) the use of interactive quizzes and creative mapping support tools.

For the first aspect, activities throughout the project were measured and evaluated quantitatively and qualitatively. For the local mapping projects, all changes to OSM were counted and validated based on the topic chosen by the students. The local government presentations are also a way to evaluate the quality of the activities. In two remote workshops, all quiz answers are then statistically analyzed to understand the level of student engagement with each topic. The humanitarian mapping process then extracts, analyzes, and visualizes data from OSM to monitor each student's process.

In the second aspect, interactive workshop tools were developed to increase online engagement and address limited physical interaction. Python-based quizzes that progressed from simple questions to discussion forums and a world map opinion sharing feature were built on the Streamlit platform for easy modification and reuse. Custom OpenStreetMap (OSM) editors were developed to increase digital accessibility, allowing students to practice mapping on OSM Sandbox servers. The iSandbox4ALL application, with a smartphone-friendly interface, followed by the iD4All application for live OSM mapping, allows students to map on smartphones as well. Finally, Python notebooks were created for data collection, statistics, and 3D map visualization, providing detailed weekly reports of student contributions (python notebook and 3D web map of the training can be found in [7]).

In conclusion the EuthMappers project is a mapping playground not only for students but also for educators. Through dynamic mapping activities, students collaborate to identify local and global challenges and address them using geospatial technology. Humanitarian mapping encourages students to develop empathy and participate meaningfully in global emergency initiatives. By involving high school students, the project has achieved cross-institutional partnerships, advanced STEAM teaching methods and technologies, and created a flexible framework for local community mapping with people from a variety of backgrounds and approaches.

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Intelligent Enough? Evaluating Collective Action in HOT Tasking Manager Mapping Projects

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Humanitarian mapping projects coordinated through the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team Tasking Manager (HOT-TM) represent a paradigmatic case of large-scale digital collaboration. Yet, while their practical utility in disaster response and preparedness is increasingly evident, the underlying collective dynamics that allow these efforts to function effectively remain under-explored. This talk builds on our recent article published in ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI) [1] that presents a comprehensive analysis of HOT-TM projects through the lens of collective intelligence.

Collective Intelligence is defined as “groups of individuals acting collectively in ways that seem intelligent [2].” Following this definition, we structured our analysis around three guiding research questions: (RQ1) What characterizes the group of individuals collaborating in HOT-TM mapping projects?, (RQ2) How is collective action organized within these projects?, and (RQ3) What evidence of intelligent action can be identified in this setting?

To answer these questions, we constructed and analyzed a dataset encompassing 746 HOT-TM projects executed between December 2021 and November 2023. Additionally, we incorporated spatial information on the area of mapped buildings using data extracted from the OpenStreetMap database. The methodology consisted of three main components. First, an initial profiling of 38,893 contributors was conducted using descriptive statistics, focusing on experience levels (beginner, intermediate, advanced), geographic location, and profile completeness. This allowed the authors to assess contributors' mapping activity, regional participation patterns, and profile richness. Second, to characterize collective action, process mining techniques were applied to over 1.8 million state transitions captured in HOT-TM event logs¹. Each task was treated as a case, with its sequence of mapping and

¹ We have made available a code repository with Python and R notebooks that document in detail the procedures followed for data collection, preprocessing, and analysis in this study. The link is <https://github.com/IAAA-Lab/Collective-Intelligence-in-Humanitarian-Voluntary-Geographic-Information-ODECO-HOT-TM>.

validation states represented as an activity trace. Using the *bupaR* package in R, we generated directly-follows graphs and trace frequency maps to reconstruct typical workflows. Performance overlays allowed us to examine state durations, throughput times, and bottlenecks. We also analyzed handover of work patterns, identifying when and how tasks moved between contributors, and measured the degree of sequential collaboration during mapping and validation phases. The analysis distinguished between individual and collaborative contributions and explored how these patterns varied by contributor expertise and project characteristics. Third, a logistic regression model was employed to investigate factors associated with task validation outcomes—used as indicators of collective intelligent action. The model included variables related to contributor attributes (e.g., experience level, location, number of contributors per task), task characteristics (e.g., building area mapped, validation time), and project-level controls (e.g., difficulty and priority).

Results show that the vast majority of contributors are beginners, who typically participate in a single project. However, a small group of highly experienced mappers—classified by HOT-TM as "advanced"—contribute to dozens of projects and assume more complex tasks. Notably, only 29% of contributors declare their country, but among those who do, the majority are based outside the regions affected by the mapping projects. This reinforces existing concerns about the limited presence of local knowledge in humanitarian Volunteered Geographic Information (VGI) initiatives [3].

Most mapping tasks are directly mapped and then validated without being split or invalidated, with a small percentage of tasks deviating from the main path (see Figure 1). However, tasks that involve higher complexity or suffer errors require more contributors and longer processing times. Roles within the mapping system are clearly stratified: while beginners dominate mapping in simpler projects, advanced mappers take the lead in complex cases and are responsible for nearly all validations. Despite the potential for collaboration in the mapping phase—through the sequential editing of tasks—true interdependence among contributors is limited. Most tasks are executed by a single mapper, and where collaboration occurs, it is often sequential and uncoordinated. This suggests that HOT-TM's microtasking design promotes a form of "collection" rather than "collaboration" [4].

Figure 1. Frequency and duration map of task states and transitions (85% of most frequent traces).

We find that advanced contributors are significantly more likely to produce validated outputs, especially when working alone. However, involving multiple contributors in a task—especially when they are less experienced—decreases the probability of successful validation. Furthermore, tasks with larger building areas or those requiring extensive validation times are less likely to be validated, suggesting that complexity and ambiguity remain major challenges.

These findings highlight a paradox at the heart of humanitarian mapping: although the system succeeds in rapidly mobilizing volunteers to produce useful geographic data, its collective intelligence is unevenly distributed and relies heavily on a small core of experienced contributors. The wisdom of the crowd is therefore not uniformly distributed; rather, it is the wisdom of a few that sustains the productivity and reliability of the system. Moreover, the absence of strong collaborative mechanisms and the limited engagement of local mappers constrain the potential for adaptive and context-aware mapping.

We conclude by reflecting on possible design improvements for platforms like HOT-TM. These include: (1) enhancing onboarding and mentorship to accelerate the transition from beginner to advanced contributor; (2) incentivizing meaningful collaboration beyond sequential task handovers; and (3) integrating local knowledge more effectively by prioritizing and rewarding contributions from mappers with relevant geographic proximity or contextual expertise. These directions not only aim to improve the efficiency of mapping but also address the deeper goal of fostering sustainable, inclusive, and context-aware humanitarian VGI ecosystems.

This work contributes to the growing body of research at the intersection of Human-Computer Interaction, Collective Intelligence, and Geographic Information Science, and provides empirical grounding for future interventions in humanitarian mapping systems.

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Conflicts of Interest: Héctor Ochoa-Ortiz is a member of the OpenStreetMap Foundation board of directors, as well, he is the president of Asociación OpenStreetMap España. He does not represent these organizations in this document.

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